

A Study on Comparison of Customer Preference between Online Parlour Website Services and Offline Parlour Services

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Abstract

As online marketing e commerce are trending in the market opportunity arose for the service sector too.

Many organization launching there e portals and website to connect with the customer and market their goods and services.

Among the trending digital marketing in service sector ola cabs, Uber cabs, swiggy, zomato and urbanclap are the live examples

My main focus of study is on comparison between online and offline parlour services.

From this study it was clear that the online parlour service is at growing stage and offline parlour is in maturity stage according to product life cycle concept.

Introduction

Digital marketing gave an opportunity to many business to grow and expand. Even service oriented business are establishing digitally to expand and get recognized globally among such business units urbanclap saloon at home (beauty parlour services) is one among the many digital marketing sites.

Online beauty care services are established by providing websites to the customer to choose the service and the date of service to be rendered at their convenient place where service provider to along with the tools and necessities to render services. Offline beauty parlour service are nothing but local parlours near to the residence where we should go to get service done. Difference between offline parlour and online parlour service.

Nature	Offline parlour	Online parlour
Comfort levels	High as we know the parlour and artist from before it seems to be friendly.	Low as every time you book different persons may approach for providing service.
Price of services	Expenses are low compare to online parlour service.	Expenses are high comparatively.
Pre booking	Pre booking is not necessary first come first service policy is opted in offline parlours.	Pre booking is must that too in advance because service providing professional slots may be full so 2 days before booking is must.
No Waiting	Customer needs to wait if the artist is already involved with other customer.	No waiting as artist will only come to provide service to customer on scheduled time
Trust issues	Customers feel satisfied and happy to go to parlours as they have trust on the artist and their work and establishments.	Customers may be doubtful about the artists service as they may not know the artists and their work.
Security issues	Customers feel safe and secure to get the services done as they have established relations with the regular parlours and their identity.	Customers may not feel safe and secured to get the service done by the artist and also their visit to home may also be unsecured any crime or theft can happen on the name of service.
Awareness	People are aware of their local beauty parlour through their friends neighbours posters etc., and also their existence and functioning	People are not much aware of the online website providing parlour service at home and their access and functioning procedures and details it is a major drawback for their business.

Literature Review

1. A Study on the Service Quality Attributes of Parlour Service Employees and Their Contribution to Customer Satisfaction in the Beauty Care Service Industry (2017)
2. Customer Attitude towards Beauty Parlour-A Study on: Persona - (2014)

Research Methodology

Sample Size

The project data is collected on information from 100 respondents who are the customers of parlour, online parlour, users of cosmetics and grooming tools.

Sampling Techniques

The sampling technique adopted was the convenient sampling technique for the consumers. The respondents for the study were chosen following the random sampling method.

Sources of Data Collection

The data collected for the study included primary and secondary data.

1. Primary Data

Primary data is the original data collected specially for the research. The method used to collect primary data is structured questionnaire.

2. Secondary Data

The secondary data for the study was obtained from

- Websites
- Online journals

Tools used for Analysis

The researcher adopted these tools for analysis:

- Percentage analysis

Findings

1. 36% of respondents visit beauty parlours more than thrice and 17% visit parlour twice in six months
2. 71% of respondents have not experienced online parlour websites service at home where as 17% respondent say it was good experience.

Observations

- Consumer reaction suggests that parlour is still market leader among all its close counter parts in the beauty and grooming segments it holds as maximum respondents opted beauty parlour compare to other segments.
- The factors like best quality, best price, comfort, full satisfaction and friendly nature attracting the customers more towards parlour than cosmetics, tools and online parlour services.
- Consumers are not showing that kind of craze in online parlours i.e., salon at home, urban clap services at present.
- Probably it could be because of the influence snatched by parlours near to home, known parlours and also customers have trust issues, security issues and ignorance of online parlour service so that they are not showing interest.
- Celebrities also affect the brand. Parlour is having the regular importance and need but online parlour service recently started its endorsement using celebrities so that can impact in future.

Suggestions

Online parlour services

- The online parlour websites must advertise their services in a easy and attractive manner by showing how to access and use their service as the study reveals 71% are not aware with online parlour websites providing services at home.
- The online parlour services must take appropriate steps to make their position in the market by providing demonstrations free of cost or at less price and make customer believe that they are true and best in providing service.
- The online parlour service providing websites must prefer good celebrities to make their brand popular and also assure the safety with their service providers.
- Now they realised the needs and investing much in endorsements using celebrities and clear-cut advertisement regarding the process of service provided.